

INTERACTIVE: A CASE-BASED FRAMEWORK FOR RISK-AWARE LEARNING IN TECHNICAL EDUCATION (TIVE = TRAINING IN INTERACTIVE VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENTS)

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Abstract. *The case study method is one of the interactive teaching approaches, enabling students to acquire academic information and skills by using it as a practical guide. Case-based technology relies on the use of specially simulated real-life industrial scenarios in the educational process for analysis, problem identification, exploration of alternatives, and selection of the most optimal solution. Consequently, the potential of case-based technology transforms it into an effective tool for developing the research competencies of future professionals and integrating their academic and research activities.*

Keywords: *interactive cases, accident investigation, case-based technologies, industrial scenario, first aid, acceptable risk skills, practical skills.*

INTRODUCTION

When selecting the interactive case to be developed, we considered that the curriculum for the "Life Safety" course allocates only two hours to the section "Recording and Investigating Workplace Accidents." These two hours cover not only workplace accidents but also "Legal and Constitutional Aspects of Life Safety." However, the telecommunications industry has seen a rise in workplace accidents. Therefore, the algorithm for recording and investigating workplace accidents was chosen as a methodology for developing acceptable risk skills for students of technical higher education institutions.

The "Life Safety" course is one of the practice-oriented subjects in technical higher education institutions. This discipline is characterized by a specific set of competencies to be developed: providing pre-medical first aid, knowledge of recording and investigating workplace accidents, understanding the basics of firefighting, and providing assistance in emergencies, all of which require objective assessment of their mastery. A mandatory requirement for the subject-specific outcomes of the "Life Safety" course is that students must acquire the skills to provide first aid to victims, extinguish fires, and more.

The modernization of practical training in the "Life Safety" discipline imposes new requirements for evaluating the practical skills and abilities acquired during the semester. This enhances the effectiveness of the educational process by improving the assessment of students' knowledge and their ability to apply skills, particularly in extreme situations.

Risk Situations. In workplace scenarios involving risk, professional training aims to develop an adequate assessment of one's capabilities in a given situation, the ability to achieve necessary results under hazardous working conditions, and the skill to do so without jeopardizing one's own life and health or that of colleagues. Risk in the course of professional activity may arise from various causes: adverse external professional environments (equipment

failure, poor ecological conditions, unfavorable social climate, etc.), as well as inappropriate human behavior in the workplace.

Currently, the issue of developing acceptable risk skills among students is particularly relevant. This is evidenced by the adoption of various laws in this area in our country. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Occupational Safety states that higher and secondary specialized vocational educational institutions are required to provide training for occupational safety specialists. It also mandates the compulsory study of occupational safety courses by students and trainees, taking into account the specific characteristics of production in various sectors of the economy and the social sphere [1].

Articles of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provide for the acquisition of information on workplace risks.

Article 22, "Rights and Responsibilities of Workers in the Field of Occupational Safety," of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that a worker has the right to receive information from the employer about working conditions, including the presence of risks of occupational and other diseases, the benefits and compensations associated with them, as well as individual and collective protective equipment [2].

Foreign researchers actively study the issues of developing acceptable risk skills. In his dissertation, Jalal Hafez Ahmad Abu-Alrop defines risk as "the likelihood that adverse events will occur unexpectedly" [3].

Eman Gabar Abdul Al Kaibi, in the abstract of her dissertation research, highlights the importance of developing and designing appropriate mathematical and software tools for information security subsystems based on the Concept of Acceptable Risk, calling this a highly relevant issue [4].

Chunguan Liu, in the abstract of his dissertation, notes that most managerial decisions are made under risk conditions due to uncertainties in the external and internal environment, random elements, lack of information, and deviations between actual and planned outcomes [5].

Sakr Sadek Sallam Nasser argues in his dissertation that it is necessary to analyze occupational risks using databases and consider potential cumulative effects of professional and ergonomic risk factors [6].

Pham Viet Zung, in his dissertation abstract, discusses how numerous risk-related issues arise from the lack of methodological and scientific justification for activities, the problem of "rare events," and the creation of "hazard models," which are recommended for implementing safety management methods considering risk factors [7].

The case method facilitates the application of theoretical knowledge to practical tasks, compensates for academic education, and helps acquire practical skills in studying the "Life Safety" discipline. It provides deeper insights into the accounting and investigation of workplace accidents. Zhao Nannan, one of many scholars studying case technologies, writes in her dissertation that for the adequate assimilation of the didactic functions of textbooks, the case study method should be used as an action algorithm. This involves students analyzing the implementation of specific didactic functions of the textbook and finding practical solutions to problems [8].

A.A. Mauri, in the abstract of his dissertation, applies the case method, which has proven its effectiveness through many years of use in both foreign and domestic schools for training specialists in management [9].

E.Yu. Lesite employs the case study method in her research to work through situations requiring the resolution of controversial or ambiguous issues by finding common ground among differences, similarities in opposites, and what is permissible in seemingly impossible circumstances [10].

Sun Lei, in the abstract of his dissertation, describes educational cases as specially prepared materials and structured descriptions of participants' activities during debates on problem resolution [11].

A.A. Lyash, in his dissertation, describes a methodology for training future informatics teachers during subject-technological preparation in higher education institutions. He emphasizes readiness for professional activities in the context of informatization and virtualization of the educational process, particularly when the case method (case study) is selected as the teaching method [12].

The aforementioned studies and source analysis demonstrate that researchers have explored the theoretical and practical foundations of applying case technologies in higher education. However, in the era of global threats and challenges to humanity's safety, no monographic studies have addressed the issue of developing acceptable risk skills through interactive cases in the study of the "Life Safety" discipline.

Let us consider the interactive format in the case "Recording and Investigating Workplace Accidents" [13]. Computer-based testing and a deeper examination of theoretical material allow students to master the course content effectively. Case participants take on the role of central characters in the situation, find solutions, and develop optimal actions for the circumstances. The focus is not on absorbing pre-prepared knowledge but on creating it.

Distinctive Features of the Interactive Case Method

The process of solving a case consists of several stages:

1. Exploring the Proposed Scenario (Case), Specifically "Recording and Investigating Workplace Accidents"

A situational case helps develop acceptable risk skills and demonstrates the application of the Acceptable Risk Concept in the workplace. This case aids in mastering the optimal action algorithm in emergencies and selecting an appropriate solution [14]. Students begin by taking an introductory test to refresh their knowledge from lectures on the topic "Recording and Investigating Workplace Accidents."

2. Collecting and Analyzing Missing Information

At this stage, students become acquainted with a specific workplace situation [15]. In the first interactive case, a workplace accident is examined, particularly a fall from a height onto a concrete floor during optical feeder installation work.

3. Examining All Possible Outcomes of the Workplace Situation and Problem Solving

At this stage, all possible scenarios for the given workplace situation are explored, and solutions to the problem are sought [16]. To formulate the optimal algorithm for "Recording and Investigating Workplace Accidents," students need to answer a series of questions.

4. Developing the Best Solution

Achieving the best solution requires thorough work at each stage of the study [17]. It is essential to remember that cases do not have a single correct solution. The goal is to find multiple or one highly effective solution for the specific situation. Additionally, cases are built on real facts and mimic real-life scenarios, but under time constraints, it is not always possible to grasp the full picture [18].

EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH

For the interactive case "Recording and Investigating Workplace Accidents", an optimal solution may involve completing the commission's work on investigating the workplace accident. However, this situation does not have one definitive resolution; the final solution depends on numerous factors considered during the interactive case study [19].

Interactive Case: "Investigation and Recording of Workplace Accidents"

Objectives:

Familiarize students with the rules for investigating and recording workplace accidents.

Study the characteristics of workplace accidents and the investigation algorithm.

Develop skills in analyzing and systematizing information.

Master the application of the investigation algorithm for workplace accidents.

Tasks:

Develop teamwork skills.

Foster an attitude of care toward one's own health and the health of others.

Enable the application of acquired knowledge and skills in unconventional situations.

Case Type:

Interactive and educational.

Case Description:

Students are presented with a scenario likely to occur in a telecommunications enterprise, along with a set of cases containing information relevant to the scenario. Students are tasked with evaluating the situation, identifying the main problem, determining its consequences, and proposing solutions.

Scenario Description:

TABLE 1. Description of the Workplace Situation

Circumstances	The electrician was working as part of a team laying an optical feeder on the territory of an automatic telephone exchange at a height of 2.75 m. At some point, he lost his balance and fell onto the concrete floor. The victim suffered serious health injuries in the form of a craniocerebral injury and a spinal fracture.
Violations	1. The employer has not ensured safe working conditions. 2. Occupational safety requirements for the operation of electrical installations have been violated.
Responsibility	Fine.

Tasks:

After reviewing the informational cases, answer the following questions, recording your responses in the table:

- a) What type of workplace accident occurred?
- b) Who needs to be notified about the accident?
- c) Develop an algorithm for investigating the workplace accident.
- d) Identify the type of workplace accident and describe the work of the investigation commission.
- e) Propose preventive measures to avoid workplace accidents.

Informational Cases

(Distributed to students for review)

Case: "Recording and Investigating Workplace Accidents" (Distributed to students)

1. Determine whether the incident qualifies as a workplace accident or a personal injury.
2. If it is a workplace accident, inform management and the injured person's relatives.
3. Call for emergency medical assistance.
4. Document the scene of the incident.
5. Assess whether the accident is classified as minor or severe.
6. Notify the relevant authorities.
7. Prepare a report using Form H-1.

To resolve this case, "Recording and Investigating Workplace Accidents", we first need to analyze the situation and identify the most appropriate solution.

The following types of incidents are subject to investigation and recording: injuries, poisonings, heat strokes, explosions, accidents, structural collapses, burns, frostbite, drownings, electrocutions, lightning strikes, damage caused by contact with animals, insects, and reptiles, acts of terrorism, and other health damages resulting from natural disasters (e.g., earthquakes, landslides, floods, hurricanes, etc.) that occur while performing work duties (including business trips) on or off the employer's premises.

A developed algorithm for solving this case is shown in Figure 1.

This algorithm outlines the sequence of actions necessary for recording and investigating workplace accidents.

Analyzing real-life scenarios increases students' interest in learning, encourages active mastery of knowledge and skills in data collection, processing, and analysis, and fosters the development of essential competencies, as well as analytical and practical skills [20].

Upon entering the "Start" section, the student undergoes an introductory test on topics such as workplace accident recording, accident investigations, and electrical injuries in industrial settings. This test is based on previously studied lecture material.

Each block of the algorithm is also described in detail. If the student answers at least 50% of the questions correctly, they proceed to the next block. Otherwise, the program redirects them to the theoretical section, where they review the material again before returning to the initial test.

FIGURE 1. Algorithm of the interactive case "Recording and investigation of industrial accidents".

When entering the section "Accident at work", the student is tested on the knowledge of the types of accidents at work.

In the next section "Reporting an accident at work", the student is tested on the

knowledge of the registration of an accident, on the knowledge of the definition of an industrial injury.

Next comes the section "**Providing first aid**", which examines the skills of providing first aid.

Next we move on to the section "**Inspection of the scene of the incident**", where the ability to adequately navigate the scene of the incident is tested.

In the section "**Results of the investigation of an accident at work**", the student is tested on the knowledge of the registration of an accident, informing the relevant authorities.

TABLE 1. Case method: summing up

Industrial accident (with explanation of choice)	List of persons who must be notified of an accident:	Algorithm for investigating an industrial accident	Determine the type of accident (minor-serious) and which authorities need to be informed about the accident. The commission's work period.	Possible measures to prevent accidents at work
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Discussion of Students' Work and Identification of Correct Actions for Accident Investigations

Consideration of questions requiring further analysis:

- a) What criteria classify an incident as a workplace accident that must be investigated?
- b) What information is recorded in the accident report by the investigation committee members?
- c) What types of liability are stipulated for non-compliance with occupational safety and health regulations?
- d) What are the measures for preventing workplace accidents?

This case method can be applied both individually and by dividing the class into groups.

The point-based rating system used in our university to evaluate students' mastery of the course "Life Safety" does not fully assess practical skills and abilities [21]. During the lesson, the instructor evaluates both theoretical and practical knowledge of the students. Final assessments use an accumulative system for all sessions within a topic or section. However, this approach does not allow for the objective evaluation of practical skills or the determination of the level of proficiency in practical abilities [22].

For assessing students in the «Life Safety» course, it is appropriate to introduce the concept of "extreme professional competence," which reflects an individual's readiness to work in suddenly complex conditions, emergencies, or extraordinary situations in both workplace and everyday settings [23].

The primary task of each individual is internal preparation for professional activities in unique conditions, mentally simulating various extreme situations, and developing strategies for optimal behavior in challenging professional environments [24].

Essential Qualities of Future Specialists:

FIGURE 2. Competencies of the future specialist

3): Let's consider the competencies that a future specialist should have in more detail (table

TABLE 3 Competencies of a specialist

№	Qualities of a future specialist	Definition of competence
1	Social competence	an indicator of the characteristic level of an individual's mastery of a range of social and psychological knowledge and moral and legal value judgments that enable him to successfully adapt and act actively in a particular social environment
2	Personal competence	these are the internal resources of an employee, which were formed under the influence of his character and personal qualities, as well as other psychological attitudes that help employees in successfully completing tasks
3	Technological competence	it is a generalized way of acting that includes not only a system of knowledge, skills and abilities, but also a system of technological means, a standard procedure for their application for the purposes of training, education, and development
4	Extreme competence	the ability to act in suddenly complicated conditions, during accidents, and disruptions to technological processes
5	Special competencies	mastery of professional activity at a relatively high level, ability to plan one's further professional development

RESEARCH RESULTS

To assess students' knowledge in the discipline Life Safety, we propose using extreme competence. This is a rather multifaceted concept that can be viewed from different angles:

- a person has the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities for rational decision-making and readiness for emergency situations, natural disasters, technological processes and damage, conflict resolution in problem situations, demonstration of skills for rational decision-making;
- determination to act actively in the event of an emergency, using a previously mastered algorithm of actions;
- determination and desire to perform the necessary action to stabilize the situation;
- a person being at the workplace at the right time.

TABLE 4 Criteria for assessing critical competence

№	Criteria/ Levels	Emergency-cognitive	Algorithmic-activity- based	Extremely reflexive
1	Reproductive	- incomplete and unrelated fragmentary knowledge on risk prevention and emergency response	- Practical implementation of a set of unrelated actions to prevent risk.	- identification of risk factors and emergency situations; - lack of readiness to prevent risks and eliminate emergency situations
2	Productive	- complete but not interconnected knowledge of risk prevention and emergency response;	- slow but conscious execution of the correct algorithm of actions to prevent risk and eliminate an emergency situation;	- identification of professional challenges to prevent risk, their transformation into a proven algorithm of actions; - acceptance of obligations to prevent risk;
3	Automatic	- complete and interconnected knowledge of risk prevention and emergency response	- automatic execution of algorithmically correctly constructed actions to prevent risks and eliminate emergency situations.	- rapid recognition and acceptance of professional challenges to prevent risks and eliminate emergencies, transforming them into well-coordinated actions; - full commitment to prevent risks and eliminate emergencies

EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH

Objective of the Pedagogical Experiment The objective of the pedagogical experiment was to substantiate and empirically assess the impact of integrating interactive case studies into the course “Life Safety” on the development of acceptable risk skills among students of technical higher education institutions.

Tasks of the Pedagogical Experiment 1. To determine the pedagogical effectiveness of incorporating interactive case studies into the curriculum of the “Life Safety” discipline. 2. To optimize the tools and approaches for developing acceptable risk-related competencies in technical university students through the use of digital interactive learning environments. 3. To evaluate the outcomes and efficiency of the proposed instructional methodology based on the integration of interactive case-based scenarios. 4. To formulate practice-oriented recommendations for the design, implementation, and didactic application of interactive case studies in the training of future specialists in technical disciplines.

Stages of the Pedagogical Experiment:

- Selection of base institutions and representative student samples for participation in the study.
- Preparation of methodological and organizational support materials.
- Implementation of the diagnostic (ascertaining) stage.
- Execution of the formative stage of the experiment.
- Conducting the control (summative) stage to verify the effectiveness of the pedagogical interventions and assess the development of target competencies.
- Statistical processing of empirical data.
- Analytical interpretation of research findings.
- Formulation of evidence-based conclusions and development of practical guidelines.

Ascertaining Stage (2021–2022 Academic Year)

This stage was aimed at diagnosing the current state of acceptable risk skills formation during the study of “Life Safety”. The research methodology included a review of scientific and pedagogical literature, analysis of educational and methodological resources, as well as interviews, surveys, and classroom observations involving instructors, students, and industry stakeholders.

Key outcomes:

- Identified gaps in methodological practices related to risk education;
- Determined course topics requiring pedagogical emphasis on risk identification and mitigation;
- Refined educational objectives for subsequent experimental stages.

Formative Stage (First Half of 2022–2023 Academic Year)

The purpose of this stage was to design, test, and integrate web-based interactive case studies into the educational process. A modular digital system was developed, alongside a methodology for its implementation and a framework for the step-by-step formation of risk assessment and management competencies.

Applied research methods:

- Pedagogical modeling and scenario construction;
- Systematization and analysis of ICT-based solutions;
- Interactive learning environment design.

Key outcomes:

- Developed a technological framework for designing interactive case studies;

- Created a structured methodology for the deployment of digital learning tools;
- Established and validated assessment criteria for measuring acceptable risk competencies.

To analyze the reliability of the results obtained in the third stage of the pedagogical experiment, statistical processing was used based on the methods of mathematical statistics. The main tool for analysis was the Student's t-test, which made it possible to determine the statistical significance of the differences between the results of the control and experimental groups, as well as the validity of the effectiveness of the implemented methodology.

Experimental Base

The pedagogical experiment was conducted in the following technical universities:

- Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi;
- Tashkent State Technical University named after Islam Karimov;
- Namangan Engineering-Construction Institute;
- Yangiyer Branch of the Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology.

Criteria for Selecting Educational Institutions

- Consistency in educational training profiles and academic specializations;
- Inclusion of the “Life Safety” course in the curriculum;
- Comparable levels of material and technical infrastructure;
- Qualified teaching personnel in the domain of occupational and environmental safety.

The primary objective of the final, control phase of the pedagogical experiment (academic year 2023–2024) was to empirically validate the effectiveness of the developed methodological recommendations for designing and applying interactive case studies aimed at fostering acceptable risk skills among students. During this phase, the experimental group received instruction based on the newly developed interactive case materials, while the control group continued to be taught using conventional pedagogical approaches and traditional case methods. To ensure the representativeness of both experimental and control groups, a preliminary diagnostic assessment was conducted to confirm the comparability of students' initial competency levels.

Selection of Respondents and Sample Formation

Participants of the study comprised third-year students enrolled in various technical disciplines, all of whom were engaged in the “Life Safety” course. Control and experimental groups were formed under equivalent initial conditions, ensuring the reliability and validity of comparative data analysis.

TABLE 5 Final results and efficiency rates after the experiment

Criterion	Number of students with developed levels of professional competencies						<i>t</i> _{critical} . (at 95%)	<i>t</i> _{experimental}	Level increase
	Experimental group			Control group					
	Automatic level (5)	Productive level (4)	Reproductive level (3)	Automatic level (5)	Productive level (4)	Reproductive level (3)			
Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi									
<i>Emergency-cognitive criterion</i>	34	56	2	18	59	18	1,97	4,18	8,7
<i>Algorithmic-</i>	42	50	0	18	58	19		5,67	11,7

<i>activity criterion</i>									
<i>Extremely reflexive criterion</i>	41	50	1	18	58	19		5,32	11,2
Tashkent State Technical University named after Islam Karimov									
<i>Emergency-cognitive criterion</i>	36	36	2	22	26	24	1,99	4,28	12,3
<i>Algorithmic-activity criterion</i>	36	36	2	22	26	24		4,28	12,3
<i>Extremely reflexive criterion</i>	34	38	2	19	27	26		4,72	13,6
Yangiyer Branch of the Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology									
<i>Emergency-cognitive criterion</i>	20	22	5	9	23	16	1,99	3,32	12,1
<i>Algorithmic-activity criterion</i>	21	24	2	9	26	13		3,81	12,4
<i>Extremely reflexive criterion</i>	22	22	3	8	25	15		4,17	14,3
Namangan Engineering-Construction Institute									
<i>Emergency-cognitive criterion</i>	14	12	3	11	14	13	1,99	2,42	10,9
<i>Algorithmic-activity criterion</i>	13	13	3	9	16	13		2,60	11,6
<i>Extremely reflexive criterion</i>	14	11	4	9	15	14		2,63	12,3

Main results:

1. Knowledge levels. The experimental group showed higher results compared to the control group in all universities and for all criteria. The greatest differences are observed for the "Algorithmic-activity" criterion, where the students of the Experimental group demonstrated significant development of skills in analyzing and algorithmizing professional activity.

2. Dispersion. The dispersion in the experimental group is lower than in the control group, which indicates greater homogeneity and stability of the results after applying the pedagogical methods.

3. Statistical significance. In all cases, the values of $T_{\text{experimental}}$ exceed the critical values of T_{critical} ($P = 0.05$ and $P = 0.01$), which confirms the statistically significant differences between the Experimental group and the control group. This means that the experimental methods have a positive effect on the development of students' professional competencies.

General conclusions:

Efficiency of the experiment. The applied teaching methods proved to be effective in increasing the level of students' professional competencies, especially in developing productive and reflective approaches to professional activity.

Statistical significance. In all universities, the differences between the experimental and control groups are significant, which proves the effectiveness of the experiment.

Recommendations. The methods used in the experimental group are recommended to be introduced into the educational process to achieve sustainable results in the development of professional competencies.

CONCLUSIONS

Improving the skills of acceptable risk in the discipline "Life Safety" is achieved by repeated study of the developed interactive cases. The acquired skills of resolving an emergency situation can be assessed according to the developed assessment criteria. Statistical processing of the results of the experiment using the Student method proved that the main ideas on the technology of developing interactive cases for developing acceptable risk skills and the methods of their use in teaching the academic discipline "Life Safety", as well as the developed methodological recommendations, made it possible to increase the effectiveness of training by an average of 12 percent.

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